

THE INTERPLAY OF GRIT AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE: IMPLICATIONS ON THE GRADE SCHOOL TEACHERS' TEACHING PERFORMANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15588556>

ABSTRACT

Educational excellence depends heavily on teacher effectiveness, yet understanding what drives superior teaching performance remains a crucial challenge in educational management. This study investigated the influence of teachers' grit and organizational culture on teaching performance among ninety-four (94) grade school teachers in the West 1 district of Cagayan de Oro City. This research employed a descriptive-correlational design involving systematically sampled grade school teachers. The study used three instruments to collect data. The first instrument measured teachers' grit using a modified questionnaire based on Baraquia's (2020) framework. This questionnaire had two parts: eight items measuring perseverance in teaching and eight items assessing passion and purpose in teaching. For organizational culture, a researcher-made questionnaire was used to evaluate quality of professional intervention with nine items, and a section on communication within the organization with seven items based on the study of Sofia, Triana, & Pratama (2023). Finally, the measure used for teachers' teaching performance was the teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings for 2024, which were obtained from the Department of Education Division of Cagayan de Oro official website to assess teaching performance. The researcher used descriptive statistical tool to describe the participants' level of grit, organizational culture and teaching performance and canonical correlation to measure if the variables are significantly correlated. Results revealed that teachers exhibited generally very high levels of grit in both perseverance and passion and purpose dimensions. The organizational culture assessment showed generally high ratings in professional intervention, and communication. Teaching performance was rated very satisfactory in

pedagogical content knowledge and personal growth/professional development. Canonical correlation analysis indicated that only perseverance and overall grit significantly influenced teaching performance, specifically in personal growth and professional development. These findings imply that while organizational culture creates a supportive environment, individual teacher characteristics, particularly grit, play a more direct role in professional success. Educational institutions may focus on developing teacher grit while maintaining supportive organizational structures to enhance teaching effectiveness and student outcomes.

Keywords: *teacher grit, organizational culture, teaching performance, professional development, pedagogical content knowledge*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a demanding profession that requires dedication, enthusiasm, and passion to effectively address its many challenges. Teachers constantly face obstacles that test their pedagogical approaches and strategies, which directly impact their effectiveness in the classroom and ultimately influence student success. The need to identify reliable predictors of educator performance has led researchers to examine factors such as teachers' grit - defined as their perseverance and passion for long-term goals - alongside organizational structure as potential indicators of teaching effectiveness.

The achievement of educational goals relies heavily on coordinated efforts among school personnel, including principals, teachers, students, and administrative staff. These interactions shape the organizational culture, which Usman et al. (2021) define as a shared way of thinking, doing things, and managing personnel. In today's increasingly global era, there is a constant need to enhance teacher performance, which can be measured through task completion, abilities, experience, and efficient resource use.

Among the various factors affecting teacher performance, organizational culture and trust emerge as significant elements. Work culture plays a fundamental role in building confidence and instilling values that align with organizational goals. Research by Fitria (2019) demonstrates that organizational culture directly affects teacher performance, with conducive school environments leading to enhanced teacher effectiveness.

While existing research has established the importance of both teachers' grit and organizational culture in educational settings, there remains a significant gap in understanding how these factors interact to influence teacher performance. This study aims to address this gap by examining the relationships between teachers' grit, organizational culture, and the quality of professional intervention and communication within educational institutions, aligning with UNESCO's Sustainable Development Goal 4 for inclusive and equitable quality education.

The study proposes that educators with high levels of grit, combined with a supportive organizational culture, are more likely to achieve exceptional performance outcomes. This research seeks to provide valuable insights for educational institutions and policymakers in developing strategies to enhance teacher effectiveness and student achievement. Through better understanding of these relationships, schools can create environments that support their teachers and foster educational excellence.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored in three fundamental theories: Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986), Duckworth's Grit Theory (2007), and Furnham's Theory of Culture (2004). These theories collectively provide a comprehensive framework for understanding how teachers' grit and organizational culture influence teaching performance through the interplay of personal characteristics, behavioral patterns, and environmental factors.

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) serves as the primary theoretical foundation, positing that human behavior is shaped through a dynamic interplay of personal, behavioral, and environmental factors. In educational settings, this theory explains how teachers' beliefs about their capabilities, combined with environmental supports and behavioral patterns, significantly impact their professional effectiveness. The theory emphasizes that teachers' behavior stems from complex cognitive processes including self-reflection, goal-setting, and strategic planning, rather than mere reactions to environmental stimuli.

Duckworth's Grit Theory (2007) introduces grit as a key determinant of long-term success, defining it as the combination of passion and perseverance for long-term goals. In educational contexts, this theory explains why some teachers maintain high performance levels despite challenges. The theory emphasizes that success requires sustained effort over time, not just intense effort on single tasks. Importantly, grit is not a fixed trait but can be developed through experience, mentorship, and deliberate practice.

Furnham's Theory of Culture (2004) completes the framework by explaining how organizational factors influence individual performance. This theory conceptualizes culture as a complex system of shared norms, values, beliefs, and behaviors that shape how groups work together. In educational settings, it explains how school culture influences teacher behavior through both explicit policies and implicit expectations, operating at multiple levels from visible artifacts to deeper underlying assumptions.

Teaching performance, serving as the dependent variable, encompasses two main components: pedagogical content knowledge and personal/professional growth. Pedagogical content knowledge involves understanding how to teach subjects effectively, requiring diverse representation tools and the ability to address student misconceptions. Personal and professional growth development includes ongoing learning experiences, mentoring systems, and support structures designed to enhance teacher effectiveness.

Teachers' grit serves as the first independent variable, combining perseverance in teaching with passion and purpose. Research demonstrates that teachers with high levels of grit create more engaging learning environments and show greater resilience in facing educational challenges. Perseverance represents their ability to maintain effort despite setbacks, while passion manifests in their enthusiasm for student learning and commitment to educational excellence.

Organizational culture represents the second independent variable, encompassing professional intervention, and communication within the organization.

The interrelationship among these variables is illustrated in Figure 1, which demonstrates how teachers' grit and organizational culture interact to influence teaching performance. The model shows that while both variables independently affect teaching performance, their combination creates a comprehensive framework for understanding teacher effectiveness in educational settings.

Figure 1. Schematic presentation showing the interplay of the variables of the study

Research Questions:

The study aimed to assess the grit and organizational culture of grade school teachers in the Southwest district of the Division of Cagayan de Oro and explore its implications in their teaching performance. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of teachers' grit in terms of:
 - 1.1. perseverance in teaching; and
 - 1.2. passion and purpose in teaching?
2. What is the level of participants' assessment of their organization culture in terms of:
 - 2.1. quality of professional intervention; and
 - 2.3. communication within the organization?
3. What is the level of teachers' teaching performance in terms of:
 - 3.1. Pedagogical Content Knowledge;
 - 3.2. Personal Growth and Professional Development?
4. Are the teachers grit and assessment of organizational culture significantly associated with their teaching performance?

Significance of the Study

This study aims to examine the relationship between grade school teachers' grit and organizational culture and their teaching effectiveness, providing valuable insights that can benefit multiple stakeholders in the educational system. The research findings will particularly assist teachers in evaluating their personal characteristics and developing targeted strategies to enhance their teaching efficacy, while also helping school administrators identify and address teachers' needs through improved support mechanisms.

The study's outcomes will serve as a foundation for enhancing organizational support across various domains, professional intervention strategies, and communication systems within educational institutions. Additionally, the research will contribute to the existing body of knowledge in educational management, providing future researchers with a basis for conducting related studies on teacher effectiveness, organizational culture, and educational leadership.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Teaching performance is a complex construct influenced by multiple factors within the educational environment. Research by Ambussaidi & Yang (2019) and Gómez & Valdés (2019) emphasizes that teacher performance is crucial for maintaining quality standards and directly impacts student achievement. Studies have identified various components affecting teaching performance, including pedagogical content knowledge, personal factors, school-related elements, and community aspects. Notably, Paz (2021) highlighted that teaching performance is significantly influenced by person-related factors such as resilience and perseverance.

Research on teachers' grit reveals its significant impact on professional effectiveness and student outcomes. Studies by Wang et al. (2021) and Widodo (2021) demonstrate that grit benefits teachers in diverse situations, contributing to improved student performance and teacher motivation. Grit encompasses two key dimensions: perseverance of effort and consistency of interest (Van Doren et al., 2019). While

Baraquia (2020) found that only the perseverance dimension significantly predicted teaching performance, other studies like Jennings (2019) emphasize how grit enables teachers to consistently strive for student achievement despite obstacles.

Organizational culture emerges as a critical factor in shaping teacher performance, with McShane and Von Gill (2020) identifying three crucial purposes: serving as a control system, acting as social glue, and creating sense-making mechanisms. Studies by Goetsch & Davis (2020) indicate that positive organizational culture motivates employees to work collaboratively and pursue organizational goals. However, contrasting findings exist, with some research (Hallinger & Heck, 2010) suggesting that organizational culture may not significantly impact teacher performance.

Professional intervention and communication within organizations play vital roles in teacher development and performance. Studies by Zhao et al. (2019) and Darling-Hammond & Cook-Harvey (2018) highlight how professional development enhances teachers' knowledge, skills, and classroom efficacy. Effective communication, particularly from school leadership, proves crucial in fostering positive work environments and enhancing teacher performance, as demonstrated by studies from Goetsch et al. (2020) and Pramahsari & Triatna (2021).

Recent research consistently demonstrates the interconnected nature of these factors, suggesting that teacher performance is optimized when strong organizational culture aligns with high levels of teacher grit, supported by effective leadership, professional development, and communication systems. This comprehensive understanding provides a foundation for developing strategies to enhance teacher effectiveness and student outcomes in educational settings.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design, following Creswell's (2022) framework, to examine the relationships between teachers' grit, organizational culture, and teaching performance. Using Taro Yamane Formula (Yamane, 1969), 94 grade school teachers from the West 1 district of Cagayan de Oro City Division were selected as participants, with every third teacher chosen from an alphabetized list to ensure fair representation.

The research utilized three primary instruments: a modified questionnaire based on Baraquia's (2020) framework to measure teachers' grit (assessing perseverance and passion/purpose), and a self-made questionnaire for organizational culture (measuring professional intervention, and communication), and teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings for 2024. All instruments underwent rigorous content validation and reliability testing through pilot testing with 30 teachers, yielding strong Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from .843 to .946 across all variables.

The study adhered to strict ethical standards, following the Belmont Report's principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. The research process began with approvals from the College Ethics Committee and Schools Division Office, followed by informed consent from participants. Throughout the data collection process, confidentiality and anonymity were maintained through coding systems and secure data storage.

Data analysis employed descriptive statistics (mean, percentage distribution, frequency counts, and standard deviation) to assess levels of grit, organizational culture, and teaching performance, while Canonical Correlation was used to examine the relationships between these variables. The scoring procedure utilized a 5-point scale for grit and organizational culture measurements, and IPCRF ratings were interpreted using standard adjectival rating equivalences.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the level of teachers' grit in terms of:

- 1.1 Perseverance in Teaching; and
- 1.2 Passion and Purpose in Teaching?

Table 1 presents a summary of the participants' self-assessment of their grit in teaching, measured across two key dimensions: perseverance and passion/purpose. The results indicate that teachers exhibit a very high level of grit, with an overall mean of 4.73. This suggests that they are deeply committed to their profession, recognize their vital role as educators, and are motivated by their ability to make a meaningful impact on students' lives.

Among the two dimensions, perseverance in teaching received the highest mean score of 4.75, signifying a strong determination to overcome challenges in the profession. Meanwhile, passion and purpose in teaching scored slightly lower at 4.71, but still falls within the very high category, highlighting the teachers' strong sense of purpose and dedication to their craft.

Table 1

Summary Table of Teachers' Grit

Dimensions of Level of Teachers' Grit	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Perseverance in Teaching	4.75	Very High	0.27
Passion and Purpose in Teaching	4.71	Very High	0.33
Overall Level of Teachers' Grit	4.73	Very High	0.28

The findings on teachers' grit provide valuable insights into their commitment to the teaching profession. The very high levels of perseverance, passion, and purpose indicate that these educators are not only dedicated but also resilient in overcoming challenges and sustaining their motivation. This high level of grit has significant

implications for teacher retention, instructional effectiveness, and student success. Schools and policymakers consider recognizing the importance of fostering and sustaining teacher grit through continuous professional development, mentorship programs, and a supportive work environment. By reinforcing perseverance and deepening teachers' sense of purpose, institutions can help ensure that educators remain motivated, inspired, and impactful in shaping the future of their students.

Research Question 2. What is the level of participants' assessment of their organizational culture in terms of:

- 2.1 Quality of Professional Intervention; and**
- 2.2 Communication Within the Organization?**

Table 2 presents the summary of the participants' assessment of their organizational culture across various dimensions. The findings indicate that the overall assessment of organizational culture is rated as high, with an overall mean of 4.41. Among the assessed dimensions, the *Quality of Professional Intervention* received the highest mean score of 4.55, indicating that teachers perceive professional development initiatives, such as in-service training, seminars, and LAC sessions, as the strongest aspect of their organization's culture. This implies that professional growth opportunities are well-structured, effectively implemented, and highly beneficial to teachers' professional development and instructional effectiveness.

Table 2.
Summary Table of the Participants' Assessment of Organization Culture

Dimensions of Assessment of Organization Culture	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Quality of Professional Intervention	4.55	Outstanding	0.49
Communication Within the Organization	4.36	Very Good	0.55
Overall Assessment of Organization Culture	4.41	Very Good	0.46

On the other hand, the dimension with the lowest mean score, though still rated as high, is Quality of Professional Intervention with a mean of 4.55. This implies that school leaders effectively provide quality professional interventions for teachers which are all necessary for their growth and development.

The high ratings across all dimensions indicate a generally positive organizational culture, where professional interventions, and communication practices contribute to a productive and supportive work environment. Effective organizational culture fosters collaboration, motivation, and a shared vision among employees. Goetsch and Davis (2020) emphasize that an organization's culture is reflected in the daily expression of its core values and expectations, shaping employee behavior, workplace norms, and overall institutional practices. This suggests that the culture within an organization plays a crucial

role in maintaining operational efficiency, promoting engagement, and ensuring the successful implementation of educational programs.

While the overall assessment is positive, the results suggest that continuous improvements can further enhance the organizational culture. Schools may benefit from refining leadership approaches to better align with teachers' needs, strengthening communication practices to ensure transparency, and expanding professional development opportunities to sustain growth and innovation. By fostering a strong, adaptable, and supportive organizational culture, schools can enhance teacher satisfaction, increase engagement, and ultimately improve educational outcomes for both educators and students.

Research Question 3. What is the level of teachers' teaching performance in terms of:

- 3.1 Pedagogical Content Knowledge; and**
- 3.2 Personal Growth and Professional Development?**

Table 3 presents the summary of the participants' teaching performance across two key dimensions: pedagogical content knowledge and personal growth and professional development. The findings indicate that the participants' overall teaching performance is rated as *very satisfactory*, with an overall mean of 3.91. This suggests that teachers demonstrate competence in delivering subject matter effectively while also engaging in continuous professional development to enhance their instructional skills.

Table 3.
Summary Table of the Participants' Teaching Performance

Dimensions of Teaching Performance	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	4.01	Very Satisfactory	0.72
Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.81	Very Satisfactory	0.67
Overall Teaching Performance	3.91	Very Satisfactory	0.61

Among the assessed dimensions, pedagogical content knowledge received the highest mean score of 4.01, interpreted as very satisfactory. This suggests that teachers possess a strong understanding of their subject areas and employ effective teaching strategies that facilitate student learning. Their ability to connect content knowledge with appropriate pedagogical methods ensures that they can engage students effectively and create meaningful learning experiences. The high rating in this area reflects the importance of teacher expertise in delivering lessons that align with curriculum standards and student needs.

On the other hand, the dimension with the lowest mean score, though still interpreted as very satisfactory, is personal growth and professional development with a mean of 3.81. This suggests that while teachers are engaged in self-improvement efforts, there may be areas for further enhancement in terms of professional learning opportunities, career advancement, and reflective teaching practices. Continuous professional development plays a crucial role in ensuring that educators remain updated with evolving instructional methodologies and educational policies. Schools may consider strengthening support systems such as mentorship programs, professional learning communities, and targeted training to help teachers further refine their skills and adapt to emerging trends in education.

The overall results indicate that teachers exhibit strong competencies in their teaching practices while also recognizing the need for ongoing professional growth. Investing in well-structured professional development programs can further enhance their instructional effectiveness and overall job satisfaction. Schools and policymakers must ensure that educators receive the necessary resources and support to sustain their growth, ultimately leading to improved student learning outcomes. By fostering a culture of continuous learning and reflective practice, institutions can empower teachers to maximize their potential and contribute to a more dynamic and effective educational system.

Research Question 4. Are the teachers’ grit and assessment of organizational culture significantly associated with their teaching performance?

- Ho₁. The teachers’ grit is are not significantly associated with their teaching performance.**
- Ho₂. The organizational culture is not significantly associated with their teaching performance.**

**Table 4.
Canonical Correlation Analysis**

Canonical loadings		R _c	R _c ²	F(4,180)	p
Teachers’ Grit	Teaching Performance	0.32	0.10	2.89*	0.02
Perseverance in teaching	Pedagogical content knowledge	-	0.13		
Passion and purpose in teaching	Personal growth and professional development	-	0.82		

Organizational Culture		Teaching Performance		.19	.04	1.16	.33
Professional intervention	-.95	Pedagogical content knowledge	-.99				
Communication within the organization	-.84	Personal growth and professional development	-.33				

*Significant at .05 level of significance.

The table 4 shows the result of a canonical correlation analysis between the teachers' grit and their teaching performance. There is a significant relationship between the teachers' grit and their teaching performance, $F(4,180) = 2.89$, $p=0.02$, $R_c = 0.32$. Because the correlation is significant, the H_01 is rejected. These variables have positive weak relationship where 10% of the variation of the teaching performance is explained by the teachers' grit ($R_c^2 = 0.10$). The canonical loadings, which represent the correlations between the observed variables and their respective canonical variates, were examined to interpret the nature of this relationship. The perseverance in teaching (loading = -1.00), passion and purpose in teaching (loading = -0.71), have a negative correlation with their canonical covariate under the teacher's grit. While the pedagogical content knowledge (loading = -0.13) have negative correlation and personal growth and professional development (loading = 0.82) have a positive correlation with their canonical variate under the teaching performance. This implies that teachers with better perseverance, passion, and purpose in teaching tend to have a higher pedagogical content knowledge but may have a lesser personal growth and professional development.

The result indicates that teachers with high grit, characterized by passion and perseverance, are more likely to persist in their profession, overcome obstacles, and maintain a positive outlook, ultimately leading to better teaching performance and student outcomes. Gritty individuals are more likely to maintain effort and overcome obstacles, even when faced with challenges or setbacks (Duckworth et al., 2016). In teaching context, grit enables teachers to persist in their profession, invest in their students' learning, and navigate the demands of the job effectively.

The table also shows the result of a canonical correlation analysis between the organizational culture and the teaching performance. There is no significant relationship between the organizational culture and the teaching performance, $F(4,180) = 1.16$, $p=0.33$. There is not enough evidence to show the relationship between organizational culture and the teaching performance. Thus, the H_02 is not rejected.

This implies that the organizational structure has no significant influence on the teaching performance. Hence, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This study found out that organizational culture does not influence teachers' teaching performance. This

indicates that even how good the communication and the professional interventions are, it has nothing to do with their teaching performance. The findings resonate with the study of Henderson and Berla (2019), indicates that organizational structure does not significantly influence bottom-line measures of success among teachers.

The study by Lee et al. (2022) further supports this notion, highlighting that transformational leadership is linked to increased supervisory coaching and performance feedback, which in turn enhances teacher engagement. However, this relationship was mediated through job resources, indicating that leadership styles must be complemented by concrete support structures such as mentoring programs, professional learning communities, and instructional coaching to have a meaningful impact on teacher performance. The absence of a direct correlation between leadership styles and teaching performance in this study may be attributed to variations in how leadership is implemented across different school contexts and the extent to which teachers perceive these leadership practices as beneficial to their professional growth.

Since perseverance and overall grit showed a significant correlation with personal growth and professional development, the null hypothesis stating that teachers' grit does not significantly associate their teaching performance is rejected only for these two variables. However, because organizational culture, and other aspects of grit did not show significant correlations with teaching performance, the null hypothesis is retained for these variables. This indicate that while organizational culture may contribute to a supportive work environment, they are not strong predictors of teaching effectiveness.

A general recommendation from these findings is for schools to focus on fostering perseverance and resilience among teachers, as these traits are linked to sustained professional growth and development. Providing structured support mechanisms such as mentorship programs, reflective practice initiatives, and ongoing professional learning opportunities can help reinforce perseverance and encourage teachers to engage in continuous improvement. Additionally, while organizational culture and leadership styles may not directly associate teaching performance, institutions should still cultivate a positive work environment that promotes collaboration, professional support, and resource accessibility. By creating a system that nurtures teacher perseverance while providing appropriate professional development opportunities, schools can enhance both teacher performance and long-term career sustainability.

Conclusions

The findings of this study substantiate Duckworth's Grit Theory, demonstrating that grit serves as a significant predictor of success in the teaching profession. The research confirms that teachers with high levels of grit demonstrate greater persistence through challenges, maintain their enthusiasm for teaching, and consistently strive for their students' success. This aligns with Duckworth's assertion that the combination of perseverance and passion for long-term goals often proves more decisive than natural talent in determining achievement.

The study further validates Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory by revealing how teachers' personal characteristics, particularly their grit, interact with environmental factors to influence their professional development and performance. The significant correlation between perseverance and professional growth underscores how teachers' beliefs about their capabilities, combined with their determination to overcome obstacles, directly impact their professional effectiveness.

Additionally, the findings support Furnham's Theory of Culture through the observed interplay between organizational structure and teacher performance. The quality of professional intervention and communication within the organization emerged as crucial elements that shape how teachers develop and perform within the educational environment.

However, the study also revealed an important nuance: while organizational culture creates the context for teacher development, individual characteristics - particularly grit - showed a more direct relationship with teaching performance. This suggests that while institutional support is important, personal attributes play a more significant role in determining professional success and growth in the teaching profession. This insight offers valuable guidance for educational institutions in balancing organizational development with individual teacher support and motivation.

These findings have significant implications for teacher development programs, and school improvement initiatives. They suggest that fostering teacher grit while maintaining supportive organizational structures may be more effective than focusing solely on institutional factors in enhancing teaching performance and educational outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, various stakeholders should take specific actions to enhance teacher effectiveness and organizational development in educational institutions. Teachers should prioritize personal grit development through goal-setting, reflective practices, and active participation in professional development opportunities, while also strengthening their resilience through stress management and collaborative networks. School administrators should implement structured grit development programs featuring resilience-building workshops, mentoring systems, and recognition programs, alongside enhanced organizational support systems that facilitate clear communication and collaborative decision-making.

The Department of Education should revise its policies to incorporate grit assessment in teacher evaluation systems and strengthen resilience-building components in training programs, while also allocating resources for teacher development and establishing platforms for best practice sharing. Future researchers should expand upon this work by conducting broader studies with larger, more diverse sample sizes and investigating additional variables affecting teaching performance,

particularly through longitudinal studies that examine the development of teacher grit over time and its long-term impact on professional growth and student outcomes.

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